

Sensing mode mismatch with the phase cameras at Advanced Virgo

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Abstract

When the waist position and/or size of an input beam are not matched to the eigenmode of a cavity, mode mismatch occurs. This leads to the generation of higher-order modes which translate as optical losses. Minimising optical losses in any gravitational-wave detector is important if advanced techniques like squeezing are to be fruitful. The phase camera, currently installed at Advanced Virgo (AdV), is a promising sensor to assist in minimising losses from mode mismatch. In this paper, the use of the phase camera to characterize the circulating beams in AdV will be shown. Moreover, how to measure mode mismatch and the importance of the phase information for such measurements will be described.

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Introduction

The improvement of the sensitivity of gravitational-wave (GW) interferometers faces many challenges, such as, reducing thermal noise of the suspended test masses, reducing quantum noise at both high and low frequencies of the detection bandwidth, minimising the presence of higher-order optical modes in the interferometer and controlling the thermal wavefront distortion due to the increased input power [1].

Wavefront sensing allows for probing mode mismatch [2], higher-order modes [3] and thermal effects [4], all of which need to be well controlled as they greatly impact the interferometer's stability and sensitivity [1]. Normally, we speak of mode mismatch when the waist size and/or position of the input beam does not match the waist size and/or position of the cavity eigenmode. For both, expanding the input beam into the basis of the cavity modes results in the addition of second-order optical modes [5]. In the presence of small mismatches, up to a few percent, it is typical to quantify mismatch as the power ratio of the second-order modes to the fundamental one.

In order to perform quantum-limited interferometry, losses from mode mismatch need to be kept below 2% [6]. While frequency-dependent squeezing is a crucial next step to improve the sensitivity of current GW detectors, optical losses couple to the vacuum state, degrading the amount of effective squeezed light in the interferometer [7]. Current GW detectors employ a dual-recycled Michelson interferometer configuration with long arm cavities as well as input and output mode cleaners. This means a large number of cavities, some of them non-trivially coupled, that need to be well mode

matched. AdV employs various sidebands at different modulation frequencies in order to do the angular and longitudinal control [8, 5] of the multiple optical cavities. A cavity is locked when the longitudinal automatic control loops are engaged and the cavity is kept at resonance. Compared to the angular and longitudinal degrees of freedom, mode mismatch control is less developed due to the difficulty of generating error signals to actuate on, especially in the context of multiple coupled cavities.

The phase cameras (PhC) installed at AdV are capable of generating amplitude and phase images of the laser beam at any beat frequency of interest. The ability to extract independently carrier and upper and lower sidebands provides a rich dynamical dataset which remains largely unexplored [9].

The PhC scans the laser beam over a pinhole photodiode. It employs a heterodyne technique to measure separately the upper and lower sidebands of up to five different modulation frequencies [10]. To do this, a frequency-shifted reference beam is combined on a beam splitter with the test beam (Fig. 1 a)). The test beam is scanned over the reference beam in a continuous archimedean spiral over 0.53 seconds, during which 16384 acquisitions are made, forming a 128x128 raw image. Digital demodulation allows for the reconstruction of amplitude and phase images at each beat frequency (Fig. 1 b)). Images are generated once per second.

Figure 1: Operation principle of the phase camera. a) Optical scheme of the phase camera and the beat frequencies measured at AdV. b) Example of phase camera amplitude and phase images for the carrier and 56 MHz sideband. The phase images were cropped according to the area where the beam is visible.

Currently, two phase cameras are operational at AdV. One looks into the recycling cavities through a picked-off beam, called B4, after the power recycling mirror (PRM). The other looks at the output of the interferometer, through a pick-off after the signal recycling mirror (SRM) and before the output mode cleaner (OMC), called the B1p beam (Fig. 2). The reference beam for the phase cameras is picked off before the input mode cleaner (IMC) and goes through optical fibers to each phase camera bench. Different noises couple to these optical fibers introducing phase noise into the measurement through the reference beam. In order to get rid of this common noise, in AdV, the phase images are constructed by subtracting either the phase of the carrier from one of the upper or lower sideband or by subtracting the two sidebands from one another (Fig. 1 b)).

The AdV phase cameras monitor mainly the carrier and two sidebands. One is the 6 MHz sideband

which is resonant in the power recycling cavity (PRC), the other is the 56 MHz which is resonant in both power and signal recycling cavities (SRC). The recycling cavities of AdV are marginally stable, this means that higher-order modes can resonate at the same time as the fundamental one. Because the sidebands are resonant in the recycling cavities they are extremely sensitive to optical aberrations, for example from the mirror polishing or from power absorbed in the mirrors. Being able to measure the carrier and both upper and lower sidebands at 6 and 56 MHz, the phase cameras have the potential to probe most defects, thermal effects and misalignments that might affect the dual-recycled interferometer (e.g. [11]). Although this is the great advantage of the PhC, it also makes analyzing its data and relating it to interferometer conditions very challenging. In order for that effort to be successful, analysis of the data must be supported by realistic simulations of a non-ideal interferometer.

In this work, we show how two simpler optical configurations of the interferometer can be used in conjunction with the phase cameras to measure mode mismatch in the arm cavities and to provide information on how to correct for it.

Figure 2: On the left, simplified single bounce configuration from the West input mirror. Optics are intentionally misaligned as part of the configuration, see main text for more details. One PhC looks at the beam picked-off after the power recycling mirror (PRM), called B4, while the other looks at the beam picked-off after the signal recycling mirror (SRM), called B1p. Both see the input beam in this configuration. Dashed lines indicate light that doesn't reach the phase cameras. On the right inset figure, comparison between only input mirror (IM) aligned and end mirror (EM) aligned plus locked arm.

Single bounce configuration and arm cavity mode mismatch

The single bounce configuration is normally used to troubleshoot the PhC, measure the modulation depth of the sidebands as well as a reference to measure the gain of carrier and sidebands in the recycling cavities. In this configuration (Fig. 2) only the IM of one of the cavities is aligned and both EM are misaligned. Additionally, both power and signal recycling mirrors are misaligned such that

no reflection from either reaches the phase cameras. In this way, both phase cameras see the input beam in the fundamental mode that bounced off the aligned IM. Since the optical path is the same in this configuration, the sidebands should be perfectly superposed with the carrier. Additionally, the relative phase difference between carrier and sidebands should simply be a flat offset from the slight difference in wavelength between each of the sidebands and the carrier (Fig. 1, right side, shows an example of amplitude and phase images in single bounce configuration for the B1p PhC).

In a next step, by aligning the EM and locking the cavity from which the single bounce is being performed, the shape of the cavity mode can be seen in the reflected carrier beam from the cavity (note that the sidebands practically do not enter the cavity and do not show any difference between this and the previous single bounce configuration). In this way, it is possible to compare the cavity mode with the input beam measured in the previous configuration, which, in the ideal perfectly mode matched case, should be the same. In order to study what can be concluded from this measurement with the PhC, optical simulations were performed.

Simulations in OSCAR

In order to understand how the reflected carrier beam from the locked cavity is different from the beam in single bounce configuration in the presence of mode mismatch, optical simulations in OSCAR were performed [12]. OSCAR is an FFT Matlab code that allows to simulate the full AdV interferometer in the steady-state. It also allows to simulate aberrations of the mirror optics as well as thermal effects by encoding mirror wavefront distortions. In this case, only a single arm cavity was simulated. While in the measurement, the single bounce configuration is necessary in order to measure the input beam, in the simulation one can directly compare the input beam to the reflected carrier beam from the cavity. This input beam is equivalent to the single bounce beam because the AdV test masses have the same curvature in both anti and highly-reflective (AR and HR) surfaces, it was also verified in simulation that this is the case.

Mismatch was simulated by detuning independently the input beam radius ($w(z)$) and wavefront curvature ($R(z)$), which are related to the complex parameter q of the input beam by [13]:

$$\frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{R(z)} - i \frac{\lambda}{\pi w(z)^2}. \quad (1)$$

The mismatch induced by detuning of the input beam was characterized by taking the power ratio between the second-order and fundamental modes on the reflected beam from the cavity. In order to compute the amount of second-order mode, the beam was modal decomposed in the basis of the cavity eigenmodes. To do this, OSCAR needs as input the radius and wavefront curvature of the fundamental mode in the desired basis. These values were extracted from the perfectly mode matched beam at the input mirror of the cavity.

As PhC observables, we looked at the radius of the reflected carrier beam with respect to the radius of the input beam (relative beam radius):

$$\Delta r_{ref} = \frac{r_{ref} - r_{inp}}{r_{inp}} \cdot 100 [\%], \quad (2)$$

and to the differential phase cross section between carrier and sidebands. In these simulations no additional misalignments or mirror aberrations maps were used as the goal was to first understand

Figure 3: AdV arm cavity was simulated and input beam radius and wavefront curvature (WfC) were detuned independently. Pannel a) shows the relative reflected carrier radius as defined in equation 2, pannel b) shows differential phase cross section between the 56 MHz upper sideband and carrier.

what to expect in the ideal case. Figure 3 shows how these observables change with the input beam parameters individual detuning.

It can be seen that, for small values of mismatch, the radius of curvature of the reflected carrier beam is sensitive to the detuning of the input beam radius only, and the differential phase cross section is sensitive to the detuning of the input beam wavefront curvature, with negligible coupling between the two. It was seen that as larger detunings are applied to either input beam parameter, both radius and phase cross section of the reflected beam are affected more significantly. Larger mismatches were not plotted, however, since typical measured mismatches of the arm cavities are of the order of a couple percent [14].

Additionally, it can be seen that for both cases of changes to either the input beam radius or wavefront curvature it is possible to infer what is the sign of the detuning applied, either above or below the ideal case. In the case of detuning the input beam radius, the reflected beam will be larger if the input beam is smaller than the ideal case, and smaller if the input beam is larger than the ideal case. In the case of detuning the input beam wavefront curvature, the differential phase cross section has positive curvature for larger wavefront curvatures than the ideal case, and negative curvature for smaller wavefront curvatures than the ideal case.

Looking at the upper left plot in Fig. 3 it is clear that, for approximately the same amount of mismatch, i.e. same amount of second-order mode, it is possible to have beams with very different radius. It was checked that in either case, the mode content of the beam is dominated by the fundamental and second-order modes. The different size in beams with the same mode content in terms of power is due to the phase of the second-order mode with respect to the phase of the fundamental one. This can be clearly seen by taking the complex overlap of the second-order cylindrical mode with the reflected carrier beam:

$$\gamma(E_{\text{ref}}, \text{LG}_{10}) = \frac{\int E_{\text{ref}} \cdot \text{LG}_{10}^* dx dy}{\sqrt{(\int |E_{\text{ref}}|^2 dx dy \cdot \int |\text{LG}_{10}|^2 dx dy)}}, \quad (3)$$

Figure 4: Amplitude (top) and angle (bottom) of the complex field overlap between the reflected carrier beam from the cavity and the second order mode in the cavity eigenmode basis.

where E_{ref} is the complex field amplitude of the carrier beam reflected from the cavity, and LG_{10} the complex field amplitude of the second order cylindrical mode (LG_{p1}) in the basis of the cavity. Normally, the norm of the overlap is computed, giving a value between 0 and 1 which corresponds to how much the two fields have the same power mode content. It is a known result that the mode mismatch coupling to the fundamental mode has a complex amplitude (see for example [15]). With this in mind, one can also look at the angle of the complex overlap, which will give us a measure of the overall phase difference between the two field distributions. Doing this in OSCAR when detuning the input beam radius, resulted in Fig. 4.

It can be seen in Fig. 4, that while the amplitude of the overlap is proportional to the mismatch, the angle is constant for detuning except for a π phase shift at 0 beam radius detuning. This phase shift corresponds to a sign change, which explains why the reflected beam is larger for a smaller input beam and smaller for a larger input beam.

Comparison with Advanced Virgo data

The data studied in this paper, was taken on April 1st 2022 [16]. First, two 5-minute measurements were taken in the single bounce configuration, one bouncing from the North input mirror, and the other from the West input mirror. Then, another 5 minutes of data were taken first with the North arm cavity aligned and locked followed by the West arm cavity aligned and locked.

We looked only at the B1p PhC which is approximately Gaussian (see Fig. 1 right side). The beam on the B4 PhC is strongly astigmatic and therefore it was not used in the analysis since some

more work is needed to reproduce the observed beam aberration in the simulation.

A bidimensional astigmatic gaussian fit was applied for each sideband and carrier from which the radius in the horizontal (r_x) and vertical (r_y) direction were extracted, first for the single bounce measurement, and then for the measurement with a single cavity locked. The change in r_x and r_y when the cavity is locked with respect to the input beam measured in single bounce was computed according to equation 2 for each x and y direction, where r_{ref} is the radius measured when the cavity is locked and r_{inp} is the radius measured in single bounce. This was done for each sideband and carrier.

As expected, the radius of the sidebands does not change appreciably if the arm cavity is locked, while the reflected carrier beam was seen to have increased. For the North arm, r_x increased by 1.6% and r_y by 13%, while for the West arm, r_x increased by 1.1% and r_y by 10.1%. There is a clear astigmatism in either case when the cavity is locked. An analysis was made showing that this astigmatism could be owed to a misalignment of the end mirror of the locked cavity in the horizontal direction (for more details, see [17]). This seems a likely explanation also given the bad meteorological conditions at the time the data was taken (see [16]). However, there is clearly an increase in the size of the reflected carrier beam in both cases, which points to having an input beam with radius smaller than it should be in order to be perfectly modematched.

Additionally, it seems that from the North arm there is a larger reflected carrier beam, corresponding to a larger mismatch, which is in agreement with other measurements of the mode mismatch in the arm cavities. By performing a number of free spectral range (FSR) scans of the arm cavities, 2% mismatch in the North arm and 1.2% mismatch in the West arm have been measured before.

For the phase information, we looked at the differential phase images and cross sections. It can be seen in Fig. 1 that, as expected from simulation, the phase difference between carrier and sidebands is constant in single bounce configuration. However, when the arm cavities are locked, some wavefront curvature is very clear (Fig. 5). While the differential phase cross section appears to have positive curvature (Fig. 5 bottom pannel), especially in the case of the north arm, the phase suffers from aberrations that are yet to be understood.

It is possible, in simulation, to detune the input beam radius and wavefront curvature in order to reproduce the mode mismatch measured with the FSR scan and the increase in r_y measured for the reflected carrier beam for each arm cavity. It was assumed that the change in r_y was only due to mode mismatch and unaffected by the supposed misalignemnt of the cavity end mirror (see [17]). First the input beam radius was changed in order to obtain a similar radius increase as the one measured. Secondly the input beam wavefront was changed in order to obtain the same amount of mode mismatch as that measured by the FSR scan method. The simulation was done including the aberration mirror maps for the IM. For the North arm it was obtained a reflected carrier beam 12.98 % larger than the input beam and 2.02 % mismatch, when injecting an input beam with radius 6.45 % smaller and wavefront curvature 5.5 % larger than the modematched case. For the West arm, it was obtained a reflected carrier beam 10.8 % larger and 1.22 % mismatch, when injecting an input beam with radius 5.7 % smaller and wavefront curvature 4% larger than the modematched case.

Conclusions

Simulations in OSCAR show that both the amplitude and phase information are needed in order to characterize the mismatch in both radius and wavefront curvature degrees of freedom. Additionally, in case of a locked cavity, both the size of the reflected carrier beam and the differential phase between

Figure 5: Differential phase images and cross sections between the 56 MHz upper sideband and carrier for both locked North arm (NA) and West arm (WA) cavities.

carrier and sidebands could potentially be used to correct for mismatch since they can provide the proper indications.

The size of the reflected carrier beam in conjunction with another independent measurement of the mismatch in the arm cavities defines uniquely both the input beam parameters, being a useful hint to correct for mismatch. This type of analysis can also be used to further study the phase information.

While the simulations were performed by detuning the input beam parameters, a simple correction of the input beam would not be enough to correct for the mismatches seen in the AdV cavities since it is not possible to tune the input beam differently for each arm cavity. This would be accomplished, for example, by thermal actuation on the compensation plates of each arm cavity or on the radius of curvature of the input mirrors. However, more simulation work is needed to understand how these degrees of freedom would affect the signals measured by the PhC in this context.

Finally, it is necessary to understand better how small misalignments of the cavity can impact the intensity images and the differential phase images so that better matching between simulations and real data is achieved. Other possible effects and noises related to the physical process of the scanning phase camera also need to be studied in detail. The work developed here will lead to an easy and reliable measurement of the mismatch in the arm cavities providing unambiguous information on how to correct for it.

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